

CRIMINAL BEHAVIOR AND ITS CONTRIBUTING FACTORS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14849888>

Abstract: This article discusses criminal behavior and the social factors contributing to it.

Key concepts: criminal behavior, conscious and unconscious tendencies, value system, moral orientation, generalized behavioral patterns, states of mental deviation, criminal conduct, psychological-volitional state of an individual, active defense reflex.

Today, ensuring peace and tranquility in our country, preventing and combating crime, achieving justice and the rule of law in our society is the sacred duty not only of law enforcement officers but also of every citizen.

The reforms being implemented in our country set the task of nurturing conscientious, noble, and selfless employees who are devoted to the defense of the Motherland, the peace of the country, and the future of the state, and who perform their duties wholeheartedly.

In this sense, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "We face complex tasks of educating young people, training and retraining personnel in psychology and other various fields" [1].

This is because the commission of crime hinders the building of a democratic state governed by the rule of law and a free civil society, the peaceful, tranquil, and prosperous life of the population, and the formation of a comprehensively developed, educated, independently thinking, and spiritually mature individual in society.

In Uzbekistan today, socio-legal control over crime is conditionally carried out in the following three areas:

- economic, social, moral, educational, legal, and other measures aimed at preventing the commission of crimes;
- a set of measures related to the implementation of operational-search, inquiry, preliminary investigation, and judicial investigation, carried out in order to ensure the inevitability of punishment for committed crimes;
- measures aimed at ensuring the execution of the punishment imposed by the court for committed crimes.

From this point of view, a systematic approach to the study of human criminal behavior and a modern understanding of possible processes are required today.

Traditionally, the causes of criminal behavior are divided into two groups - social and biological. However, analysis of many manifestations of behavior deviating from moral norms (rules) leads to the conclusion that this problem needs to be studied differently, that is, systematically-integrated (integrated).

It is advisable to include a system-forming factor called "psychological" in social or biological factors, and to call all the problems associated with the causal connections (determination) of human behavior socio-psychological-biological factors. The fact that the

"psychological" aspect is located in the middle means that it has a unifying function for both social and biological factors.

When discussing the causes of criminal behavior, we first dwell on the basic principles of problem analysis.

1. Criminal behavior, like normal behavior, is multifactorial; it is not a consequence of one or even several causes. However, the interconnectedness and probabilistic nature of the individual moral picture taken separately with many factors does not mean that it cannot be studied. In this regard, the identification of typical individual-psychological characteristics and moral views of the individual is of paramount importance.

2. Criminal behavior differs from positive behavior both in its content and psychoregulatory characteristics. A person's behavior is distinguished by their needs, a system of conscious and unconscious inclinations, and the characteristics of setting and achieving goals. If we depict it as a diagram, it looks like this.

The behavior of most criminals is characterized by an inability to adapt to social values (deadaptation) and shortcomings in self-management. When an individual's self-regulation capabilities are low, their antisocial inclinations and habits are not only uncontrolled but also become goal-forming mechanisms of behavior.

3. Criminal behavior is carried out on the basis of the individual's motivation to protect (justify) their social responsibility, the devaluation of generally accepted social values. A person's behavior is connected with their needs and sphere of orientation, the system of values they adopt, and the level of enjoyment of universal human culture.

4. Criminal behavior is conflict behavior, always based on internal contradictions in society, in social groups, between an individual and a social group, between individuals, and, finally, in the individual himself. The system of external states in human behavior is manifested through the system of internal mental factors formed in it. These internal psychological factors include:

- value system;
- moral orientation;
- generalized methods of behavior;
- Psychodynamic characteristics of self-regulation.

5. Neither objective nor subjective factors can be separated in human behavior. Social factors directly influence people's behavior through internal personal, individual-psychological phenomena (and this sometimes creates the illusion of a "criminal nature").

6. The less socialized the personality (this is usually a characteristic feature of the criminal personality), the higher the probability of the dominance of biological factors. The more limited the development of human consciousness, the greater the role of hierarchically lower levels of motivation in their behavior.

According to criminologists (Z.S. Zaripov and I. Ismailov, et al.), the process of criminal behavior formation is divided into the following categories: a) the process of criminal behavior formation associated with the violation of personal needs and interests; b) processes associated with the difference (contradiction) between personal needs (interests) and capabilities; c) processes associated with the violation of a person's spiritual and legal perception, values, and social orientation; d) processes associated with shortcomings and omissions in decision-making and implementation [2].

The process of criminal behavior includes the following main components: motivation, decision-making, and its implementation. Based on the idea that any socially significant act is the result of a connection between the individual's characteristics and the external environment, the process of a specific criminal act can be described as follows:

Russian scientist G. A. Avanesov identifies the following conditions that negatively affect human behavior:

- neuropsychiatric disorders (psychopathies, neurostenias, conditions at the boundary of illness and health), which increase the excitability of the nervous system, cause an inadequate reaction and make it difficult to socially control movements;
- psychophysiological stress that leads to various psychosomatic, allergic, toxic-related diseases and serves as an additional criminal factor [3].

Mental anomalies (deviations from the norm) have hereditary (genetic) roots, and neuropsychiatric disorders can only cause criminal behavior under the influence of an unfavorable environment.

As early as the 1920s, psychiatrists (Antonyan Yu.M., Borodin S.A., Vinogradov M.V., Golub S.A., et al.) emphasized the connection between the type of criminal behavior and mental anomaly. For example, according to the Russian scientist Yu.M. Antonyan,..."persons with a low level of mental, intellectual coefficient, unable to adapt to everyday life, commit theft, and sometimes murder, in order to satisfy their base needs. They easily join the ranks of ordinary thieves due to their instability and susceptibility to external influences; bandits and malicious killers are more easily formed from individuals with meaningless psychological feelings and strong base inclinations compared to others; individuals distinguished by pathological excitability easily quarrel with others over trivial matters and disrupt public order" [4].

The mental quotient (coefficient) of individuals with psychological anomalies constitutes approximately 70% of all criminals.

It has been observed that crimes involving physical violence (murder, rape, infliction of bodily harm) and hooliganism are more frequently committed by individuals in a state of psychological anomaly. For instance, when forensic psychiatric examinations were conducted on minors who had committed crimes such as murder, rape, and infliction of bodily harm, it was found that three out of five of them had various anomalies that contributed to their criminal acts. Among the offenses committed by minors registered with the relevant service sectors of internal affairs bodies, 23-43% were carried out by young people with varying degrees of mental anomalies. Analysis of the presence of anomalies in the total number of individuals who committed serious crimes using physical force revealed anomalies in 33% of individuals, organic damage to the central nervous system in 19%, traumatic brain injury in 18%, and signs of chronic alcoholism in 17% [5].

In this context, one can observe quarrelsome behavior, heightened reactivity, spontaneous emergence of negative tendencies, and weakness in the mechanism of managing one's behavior with positive values and motivations in the conduct of most criminal individuals.

All these behavioral manifestations are attributed to genetic anomalies - Klinefelter syndrome (excess X-chromosome - 47/XXY syndrome or excess Y-chromosome - 47/XYY syndrome). In this case, the excess X-chromosome is associated with excessive aggressiveness, while the excess Y-chromosome is linked to deviations (anomalies) in goal-setting and achievement, as well as disorders in volitional control of behavior [5].

Of course, the mental and volitional state of the individual comes to the forefront in the commission of a crime, and this gives rise to the opinion that this is their primary cause. In essence, the psychological factors themselves arise in the real conditions of the criminal's personality formation.

In human behavior, the system of external factors is determined by the system of internal conditions. Therefore, the unity of objective and subjective factors is evident in every crime. Neither external factors nor internal conditions create a moral act on their own.

In this sense, the dependence of spontaneously arising inclinations on random circumstances is characteristic of most criminals. The fragmentation of the personality self-regulation system is one of the main psychological aspects that distinguishes most criminals from each other. When certain selfish aspirations of criminals acquire an antisocial character, their moral system is regulated at the level of subconscious inclinations.

The subconscious mechanisms of psychological control are manifested in all purposeful actions, in a large-scale system of moral views. The lower the level of mental development of a person (this trait is characteristic of most criminals), the greater the role of subconscious mechanisms for regulating behavior.

A socialized individual is stable and whole in all situations and conditions. The criminal is dependent on the situation.

Individuals with criminal behavior differ from each other, as well as from individuals adapted to social life and law-abiding individuals, by their upbringing and negative behavioral traits formed under various conditions of social life and activity.

There is neither a "criminal psyche" nor a "criminal succession." At the same time, both the psyche and its natural conditions are "involved" in any moral act, including unlawful actions

In a person whose social views are not firm, even their natural inclinations are observed in forms of antisocial morality, that is;

sexual instinct - in rape;

active defensive reflex - in aggression against a person;

The self-preservation instinct can manifest in desertion.

By legal characteristics, the same criminal act can arise from different psychological factors. For example, theft has been observed to be committed both through the perpetrator's personal direction, weak willpower and trustfulness, and pathological characteristics.

Personal qualities manifested in a person's criminal act indicate not "some general defects in legal consciousness," but specific moral and psychological characteristics (stinginess, cruelty, social negativism).

The conducted research revealed significant psychological differences between criminals and law-abiding individuals. That is, the scale analysis revealed that the law-abiding group of subjects significantly surpassed the criminals in assessing their socio-positive attitude towards all basic values and the meaning of their lives. The differences between criminals and law-abiding individuals were clearly manifested in such values as social environment, activity, artistic enjoyment, marriage, love, children, and family [6].

Some lawyers link most crimes to the criminogenic situation, which in itself gives rise to a crime and creates conditions for its commission.

The criminogenic situation at the time of the crime is considered a special level of a person's interaction with the environment. In this connection, the propensity of a person with negative traits to commit a crime under the influence of the criminogenic situation turns into a certain behavior. The influence of a specific life situation on the commission of a specific crime by a person has the following characteristics:

Crimes are committed not due to suddenly arising criminogenic situations, but due to certain stable personal qualities and values of a person.

For an honest person who obeys the law and has a high degree of self-control, there are no and cannot be "criminal" situations. The situation itself cannot give rise to a crime; it can only be suitable for the realization of certain views and goals of a person with antisocial behavior.

In conclusion, it can be said that every person has positive behavior, and if this behavior is understood and decisions are made freely and correctly, they will not become a slave to the situation.

However, the lower the level of mental control of a person's behavior, the greater the significance of situational circumstances in their behavior. Most criminals are indeed characterized by their behavior being situational, which is a characteristic feature of their personality.

A person actively acts only because of something, an event that has a certain value for them. The value system is individual and determines a person's mental activity: what is vitally important for one person may not be so important for another.

A person's behavior is oriented based on a system of values. Some people unhesitatingly save a stranger from the danger of death, while others unhesitatingly stab a relative with a knife - everything depends on which aspects of life are important for one or another person. The system of socially positive values is not innate, but is formed in the process of upbringing in society..

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